

Developing Leadership and Teamwork Skills of Pre-Service Teacher through Learning Camp

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II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Abstract—This study aimed to 1) develop pre-service teachers' leadership skills through camp-based learning, and 2) develop pre-service teachers' teamwork skills through camp-based learning. An applied research methodology was used. The target group was derived from a purposive selection. It involved 32 fourth-year students in Early Childhood Education Program enrolling a course entitled Seminar in Early Childhood Education provided during second semester of academic year 2013. The treatment was camp-based learning activities which applied a PDCA process including four stages: 1) plan, 2) do, 3) check, and 4) act. Research instruments were a learning camp program, a camp-based learning management plan, a 5-level assessment form for leadership skills and a 5-level assessment form for assessing teamwork skills. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Results were: 1) pre-service teachers' leadership skills yielded the before treatment average score at $\bar{x}=3.4$, S.D.=0.62 and the after-treatment average score at $\bar{x}4.29$, S.D.=0.66 pre-service teachers' teamwork skills yielded the before-treatment average score at $\bar{x}=3.31$, S.D.=0.60 and the after-treatment average score at $\bar{x}=4.42$, S.D.=0.66 Both differences were statistically significant at the .05 level. Thus, the pre-service teachers' leadership and teamwork skills were significantly improved through the camp-based learning approach.

Keywords—Learning camp, leadership skills, teamwork skills.

I. INTRODUCTION

HUMAN development is the most important factor that drives the organization to the desired direction. It is impossible to improve education without teacher development. Education system needs to develop its human resources; teachers, students and supporting personnel [1]. Educational personnel must be qualified in terms of I.Q. (Intelligence Quotient), M.Q. (Moral Quotient) and E.Q. (Emotional Quotient). Therefore, becoming a good teacher requires teacher accountability which means devoting time to improve students' ability and caring for their development.

Learning camp is the extracurricular activity that helps integrate knowledge and skills of students of Faculty of Education in order to prepare them to be high-quality future teachers according to the aforementioned qualities. Students will learn to socialize, solve problems, exchange visions, leadership and develop team working skills [2], [3]. Learning camp, then, was introduced to Seminar in Early Childhood Education, one of the courses of the Faculty of Education, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University with the intention to cultivate the high-quality future teachers.

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A. Leadership

Leadership is the process that a leader takes the form of influence toward followers or using a position to make group members follow in order to achieve a defined goal. The processes include using power, group dynamics, persuasion, communication, interaction, and coordination. Leadership trait theory is one of the earliest theories of leadership. It states that leaders are born, not made. There are defined personality traits that distinguish leaders from followers. In other words, leaders are different types of people from followers. However, behavioral theories of leadership state that it is the behavior of leaders that distinguishes them from their followers. In other words, leadership is a skill that can be taught. Situational leadership theories state that a leader emerges to fit the situation. Different people will take the lead in different situations. This suggests that different situations require different skills.

Kirkpatrick and Locke [4] suggest that there are key traits which help people to acquire the necessary skills for leadership, develop a vision for themselves and others, and then implement the vision. They suggest that research shows that the key traits for leaders are: drive, leadership motivation, honesty and integrity, self-confidence, cognitive ability, and knowledge of the business.

Pierce and Dunham [5] suggest the leadership process model. The model shows the relationship between four key factors that contribute to leadership success or failure. These are:

- 1) The Leader: This is the person who takes charge, and directs the group's performance.
- 2) Followers: These are the people who follow the leader's directions on tasks and projects.
- 3) The Context: This is the situation in which the work is performed.
- 4) Outcomes: These are the results of the process.

The model shows the way in which the leader, the followers, and the context combine to affect the outcomes. It also shows how outcomes feedback to affect the leader, the followers, and the context. The model highlights that leadership is a dynamic and ongoing process.

B. Teamwork Skills

Teamwork is the process of working collaboratively with a group of people in order to achieve a goal. Teamwork means that people will try to cooperate, using their individual skills and providing constructive feedback, despite any personal conflict between individuals.

The famous teamwork theory named Tuckman's model or team stages model [6] is widely known as a basis for effective team building. The model suggests that teams grow through four common phases: forming, storming, norming and performing.

The forming phase is an initial stage of team development during which individuals have not yet gelled together. Everybody is busy finding their place in the team and sizing each other up. The storming phase is a stage when people begin to see themselves as part of a team. However, they may challenge each other, and the team leader, about such things as what the team is doing, and how things should be done. This may result in some loss of performance or focus on the task. The norming phase is where team members start to come together, developing processes, establishing ground rules, clarifying who does what, and how things will be done. This phase is characterized by a growing sense of togetherness. The performing phase is increased focus on both the task, and on team relationships, combine to provide synergy. Performance is delivered through people working effectively together.

The ability to work well in teams is a skill set on its own. However, some related traits correlate with good teamwork including

- 1) Listening skills: The use of teams in the workplace is intended to foster sharing and debate about ideas and alternative solutions. Strong listening skills help a member performs better by showing support of others when they speak, along with better understanding the ideas they share.
- 2) Persuasion: While listening to the ideas of other team members, a knowledgeable team member must often use his/her skills of persuasion to convince others to go along with his/her suggestion. Teams often use different approaches to come to agreements, but in certain situations, the team member with the best experience in a given situation needs to step up and sell that experience and point of view to ultimately bring out the best solution.
- 3) Accountability: Teams often distribute tasks to different team members. To achieve success, it is important that each team member accept accountability and complete his/her duties in a timely fashion. Along with being accountable for task completion, the skill of accountability means that you acknowledge and take responsibility for mistakes.
- 4) Cooperation: It is a general skill that encompasses a helpful nature and willingness to participate actively within the team. Work teams succeed only when all members are fully engaged in sharing ideas and performing tasks.

C. Camping

Organized camping is a community of persons living together as an organized group usually in an outdoor setting, under the directions of designated leaders. The camp program consists of the total of all experiences or events in the camp, whether structured or not and/or associated with the outdoors. Four components of organized camping are:

- 1) Focuses on natural environment in outdoor setting
- 2) Consists of the total experiences
- 3) Revolves around group living experiences
- 4) Relies on trained and well-qualified staff

Types of organized camping are: resident camps, trip/travel camps, day camps, special camps, school camps, and conference and retreat centers. Thus, organized camping is a creative educational experience, in terms of living together in the outdoors, using resources from the natural environment around them to develop physical, social, and psychological characteristics under guidance of trained camp leaders [3].

III. OBJECTIVES

- 1) To develop pre-service teachers' leadership skills through camp-based learning.
- 2) To develop pre-service teachers' teamwork skills through camp-based learning.

IV. SCOPE OF RESEARCH

A. Scope of Population

The target group was derived from a purposive selection. It involved 32 fourth-year students in Early Childhood Education Program enrolling a course entitled Seminar in Early Childhood Education provided during second semester of academic year 2013

B. Scope of Content

- 1) PDCA process includes four stages: 1) plan, 2) do, 3) check, and 4) act. The outdoor activities were designed to cover 5 main activities: being together as a group, recreation for education, outdoor living, social adaptation and camp management.
- 2) Leadership [7], [8] is the ability to lead or to motivate other people to follow willingly in order to achieve the goal. Students will be trained to set the goal, be honest, be creative, be determined to overcome barriers and develop the personalities to motivate others.
- 3) Teamwork skills [9] mean the collaborative work of members of the group in order to achieve the shared goal. The members of the group must accept the same goal through participating in planning and determining to overcome barriers. Respecting others and compromising principle are the key factors that lead to group success.
- 4) The content according to the course Seminar in Early Childhood Education which is the required course in the 2009 Curriculum of Bachelor of Education, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, for the fourth-year students. The learning objectives are to enable students to analyze critical issues in early childhood education; collect data and present the analyzed information to public in the form of seminar. This will develop the desired qualities: listening to others, honoring others' ideas and managing argument.

C. Variables

- 1) Independent Variable: Learning Camp
- 2) Dependent Variable: Leadership and Team working Skill

V. RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

A. Learning Camp Plan

The PDCA cycle [10] was used as the main idea of the learning camp plan.

P (Plan) means the process before the implementation of the project which includes:

1. Survey of the needs from school administrators, teachers and other stakeholders.
2. Lecture knowledge on learning camp and collaborate to set the goal.
3. Propose the project for approval.
4. Set up the timeline for implementation.
5. Arrange the meeting among students for the detail of the implementation.
6. Publicize the project.

D (Do) means implementation of the project which covers:

7. Lecture on camp management.
8. Co-operate all units to provide the camp equipment.
9. Prepare documents, tools, camp site for camp activities and set up the camp diagram.
10. Arrange the meeting among students who are the staff for the detail of each implementation stage.
11. Send the detail to the experts to examine.
12. Implement the project according to the plan.

C (Check) means the process of mentoring and assessing the project during implementation which includes:

13. Assess the overall view of the implementation of learning camp.
14. Observe the leadership and team working skills of the camp staff.
15. Observe the participation.
16. Evaluate the principal's and the teachers' satisfaction.

A (Act) means the follow-up process after the implementation which includes:

17. Conclude the camp learning project.
18. List all problems and recommendations for improvement.
19. Make a final project report.

B. Observational Form for Leadership and Team Working Skills

Likert's Rating Scale to observe the leadership (20 items) and team working skills (15 items) was used for this study. Each scale was designed for the raters to rate five bands: highly observed (very good), rather highly observed (good), average, poorly observed and not observed of the leadership/team working skills.

VI. PROCEDURE

The learning camp project was implemented twelve weeks continuously every Tuesday during eight a.m. to five p.m. After the twelve weeks of data collection, the researcher

analyzed the data by using Mean, Standard Deviation, and T-test.

VII. RESULTS

As shown in Tables I and II, pre-service teachers' leadership after the implementation was observed higher than before the implementation in all items.

Observed from the results, the leadership items that were observed "good" (before) and "very good" (after) levels were comprehending individual differences, being patient, having conflict-reduced skill, being responsible and being self-confident. For the leadership items that were observed "average"(before) and "good" (after) were being goal-oriented, being communicative, being disciplined, being intentional and moral, having problem-solving skill, being extroverted, having intelligible skill, having problem-confronted, being sociable, being creative, being actively learned, being co-operative and having pleasant personality.

TABLE I
MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE LEARNING CAMP STAFF LEADERSHIP BEFORE AND AFTER THE IMPLEMENTATION

Leadership	Before		Level	After		Level
	\bar{x}	S.D.		\bar{x}	S.D.	
being goal-oriented	3.34	.60	average	4.18	.64	good
being communicative	3.45	.62	average	4.21	.60	good
being disciplined	3.25	.56	average	4.06	.66	good
being intentional and moral	3.43	.61	average	4.15	.62	good
having problem-solving skill	3.62	.70	good	4.31	.78	good
being extroverted	3.46	.67	good	4.34	.60	good
comprehending individual differences	3.68	.59	good	4.53	.62	very good
having decision making skill	3.18	.59	average	4.09	.73	good
having intelligible skill	3.43	.66	average	4.21	.65	good
being patient	3.65	.54	good	4.56	.66	very good
having problem-confronted	3.43	.56	average	4.28	.68	good
being sociable	3.43	.56	average	4.31	.78	good
having team working skill	3.38	.53	average	4.46	.71	good
being creative	3.25	.56	average	4.03	.59	good
being actively learned	3.18	.64	average	4.09	.64	good
being co-operative	3.40	.66	average	4.15	.62	good
having conflict-reduced skill	3.50	.67	good	4.50	.62	very good
being responsible	3.65	.65	good	4.62	.65	very good
being self-confident	3.39	.55	average	4.56	.56	very good
having pleasant personality	3.21	.70	average	4.18	.78	good
results	3.45	.62	average	4.29	.66	good

*statistically significant at.05 level

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF LEADERSHIP BEFORE AND AFTER THE IMPLEMENTATION

Leadership	Number of students N=32	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation S.D.	T-Score
Before the learning camp	32	3.45	0.62	12.667**
After the learning camp	32	4.29	0.66	

t-score at df =31 = 12.667 **statistically significant at.05

In Tables III and IV, pre-service teachers' team-working skills after the implementation was observed higher than before the implementation in all items.

Observed from the results, the team-working skill items that were observed “average” (before) and “very good” (after) levels were being well-managed of positioning group members, being able to accomplish tasks successfully, being responsible, having a good relationship with group members, creatively expressing opinions and getting along well with other group members. For the team-working skill items that were observed “average”(before) and “good” (after) were being goal-oriented with others, being adaptive, being punctual, being strict to the plan, being able to stop conflicts, showing an appropriate leadership, being attentive to the group tasks, being attentive to the group tasks, being actively involved and being able to accomplish tasks in time.

TABLE III
MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE LEARNING CAMP STAFF
TEAMWORK SKILLS BEFORE AND AFTER THE IMPLEMENT

Team working skills	Before		Level	After		Level
	\bar{x}	S.D.		\bar{x}	S.D.	
being goal-oriented with others	3.15	.44	average	4.21	.55	good
Being adaptive	3.25	.50	average	4.34	.60	good
being well-managed of positioning group members	3.31	.53	average	4.50	.62	very good
being punctual	3.28	.68	average	4.28	.77	good
being strict to the plan	3.21	.49	average	4.31	.69	good
being able to stop conflicts	3.09	.64	average	4.06	.61	good
showing an appropriate leadership	2.96	.59	average	4.03	.69	good
being attentive to the group tasks	3.15	.67	average	4.34	.65	good
being actively involved	3.43	.66	average	4.43	.71	good
being able to accomplish tasks in time	3.37	.65	average	4.46	.71	good
being able to accomplish tasks successfully	3.33	.56	average	4.65	.65	very good
being responsible	3.43	.62	average	4.59	.66	very good
having a good relationship with group members	3.35	.54	average	4.65	.60	very good
creatively expressing opinions	3.28	.58	average	4.62	.65	very good
getting along well with other group members	3.37	.70	average	4.75	.56	very good
results	3.31	.60	average	4.42	.65	good

*statistically significant at.05 level05.

TABLE IV
COMPARISON OF TEAMWORK SKILLS BEFORE AND AFTER THE IMPLEMENTATION

Teamwork skills	Number of students N=32	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation S.D.	T-score
Before the learning camp	32	3.31	0.60	10.343**
After the learning camp	32	4.42	0.65	

t-score at df =31 = 10.343 **statistically significant at.05

VIII.CONCLUSION

It was obviously shown that the scores before and after the learning camp implementation were significantly different in that the scores of leadership after the implementation were observed higher than those of before the implementation and the scores of teamwork skills after the implementation were observed higher than those before the implementation which conform with [11] and [12].

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) There should be more studies on other desired attributes by learning camp projects.
- 2) There should be the comparative studies of leadership and teamwork skills of each year of university students.
- 3) There should be the on-going projects on the purpose to promote students' desired attributes

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